

Temperature-Sombor and Temperature-Nirmala Indices

V. R. Kulli

Department of Mathematics, Gulbarga University, Gulbarga 585106, India

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published online: 24 September 2022 Corresponding Author: V. R. Kulli	In this paper, we introduce the temperature-Sombor index, modified temperature-Sombor index and temperature-Nirmala index of a graph. Also we compute these temperature indices for some standard graphs and tetrameric 1,3-adamantane. Furthermore, we establish some properties of newly defined temperature-Sombor index and temperature-Nirmala index.
KEYWORDS: temperature Sombor index, modified temperature Sombor index, temperature Nirmala index, graph, tetrameric 1,3-adamantane.	

I. INTRODUCTION

In this paper, we consider only finite, simple, connected graphs. Let G be such a graph with vertex set $V(G)$ and edge set $E(G)$. The degree $d_G(u)$ of a vertex u is the number of vertices adjacent to u . For basic notations and terminologies, we refer [1].

In [2], the temperature of a vertex u of a graph G is defined as

$$T(u) = \frac{d_G(u)}{n - d_G(u)}$$

where n is the number of vertices of G .

In [3], the first temperature index of a graph G is defined as

$$T_1(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [T(u) + T(v)].$$

The second temperature index [4] of a graph G is defined as

$$T_2(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} T(u)T(v).$$

Recently, some temperature indices were studied, for example, in [5, 6, 7, 8].

We propose the temperature Sombor index of a graph G and it is defined as

$$TSO(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \sqrt{T(u)^2 + T(v)^2}.$$

Considering the temperature Sombor index, we define the temperature Sombor exponential of a graph G as

$$TSO(G, x) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} x^{\sqrt{T(u)^2 + T(v)^2}}.$$

We propose the modified temperature Sombor index of a graph G and it is defined as

$${}^mTSO(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \frac{1}{\sqrt{T(u)^2 + T(v)^2}}.$$

Considering the modified temperature Sombor index, we define the modified temperature Sombor exponential of a graph G as

$${}^mTSO(G, x) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} x^{\frac{1}{\sqrt{T(u)^2 + T(v)^2}}}.$$

Recently, some Sombor indices were studied, for example, in [9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32].

We define the temperature Nirmala index of a graph G as

$$TN(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \sqrt{T(u) + T(v)}.$$

Considering the temperature Nirmala index, we define the temperature Nirmala exponential of a graph G as

$$TN(G, x) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} x^{\sqrt{T(u) + T(v)}}.$$

Recently, some Nirmala indices were studied, for example, in [33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45].

In [46], the F - temperature index of a graph G is defined as

$$FT(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \left[T(u)^2 + T(v)^2 \right].$$

We define the temperature misbalance prodeg index of a graph G as

$$TMPI(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \left[\sqrt{T(u)} + \sqrt{T(v)} \right].$$

We put forward the temperature inverse sum indeg index of a graph G and defined it as

$$ISI_T(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \frac{T(u)T(v)}{T(u)+T(v)}.$$

In this paper, we compute the temperature-Sombor index, modified temperature-Sombor index and temperature-Nirmala index for some standard graphs and tetrameric 1,3-adamantane. Also we establish some properties of newly defined temperature-Sombor index and temperature-Nirmala index.

II. RESULTS FOR SOME STANDARD GRAPHS

Proposition 1. If G is r -regular with n vertices and $r \geq 2$,

$$\text{then } TSO(G) = \frac{nr^2}{\sqrt{2}(n-r)}.$$

Proof: Let G be an r -regular graph with n vertices and $r \geq 2$

and $\frac{nr}{2}$ edges. Then $T(u) = \frac{r}{n-r}$

$$\begin{aligned} TSO(G) &= \frac{nr}{2} \sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{n-r}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{r}{n-r}\right)^2} = \frac{nr}{2} \frac{\sqrt{2}r}{n-r} \\ &= \frac{nr^2}{\sqrt{2}(n-r)}. \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 1.1. Let C_n be a cycle with $n \geq 3$ vertices. Then

$$TSO(C_n) = \frac{2\sqrt{2}n}{n-2}.$$

Corollary 1.2. Let K_n be a complete graph with $n \geq 3$ vertices. Then

$$TSO(K_n) = \frac{n(n-1)^2}{\sqrt{2}}.$$

Proposition 2. If G is r -regular with n vertices and $r \geq 2$,

$$\text{then } {}^m TSO(G) = \frac{n(n-r)}{2\sqrt{2}}.$$

Proof: Let G be an r -regular graph with n vertices and $r \geq 2$

and $\frac{nr}{2}$ edges. Then $T(u) = \frac{r}{n-r}$

$${}^m TSO(G) = \frac{nr}{2} \frac{1}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{n-r}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{r}{n-r}\right)^2}} = \frac{nr}{2} \frac{(n-r)}{\sqrt{2}}$$

$$= \frac{n(n-r)}{2\sqrt{2}}.$$

Corollary 2.1. Let C_n be a cycle with $n \geq 3$ vertices. Then

$${}^m TSO(C_n) = \frac{n(n-2)}{2\sqrt{2}}.$$

Corollary 2.2. Let K_n be a complete graph with $n \geq 3$ vertices. Then

$${}^m TSO(K_n) = \frac{n}{2\sqrt{2}}.$$

Proposition 3. If G is r -regular with n vertices and $r \geq 2$,

$$\text{then } TN(G) = \frac{nr\sqrt{r}}{\sqrt{2}\sqrt{n-r}}.$$

Proof: Let G be an r -regular graph with n vertices and $r \geq 2$

and $\frac{nr}{2}$ edges. Then $T(u) = \frac{r}{n-r}$

$$\begin{aligned} TN(G) &= \frac{nr}{2} \sqrt{\left(\frac{r}{n-r}\right) + \left(\frac{r}{n-r}\right)} \\ &= \frac{nr\sqrt{r}}{\sqrt{2}\sqrt{n-r}}. \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 3.1. Let C_n be a cycle with $n \geq 3$ vertices. Then

$$TN(C_n) = \frac{2n}{\sqrt{n-2}}.$$

Corollary 3.2. Let K_n be a complete graph with $n \geq 3$ vertices. Then

$$TN(K_n) = \frac{n(n-1)^{3/2}}{\sqrt{2}}.$$

III. RESULTS FOR TETRAMERIC 1,3-ADAMANTANE

In Chemistry, diamondoids are variants of the carbon cage known as adamantane (C_{10}, H_{16}), the smallest unit cage structure of the diamond crystal lattice. We focus on the molecular structure of the family of tetrameric 1,3-adamantane and it is denoted by $TA[n]$. Let G be the graph of tetrameric 1,3-adamantane $TA[n]$. The graph of tetrameric 1,3-adamantane $TA[4]$ is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The graph of tetrameric 1,3-adamantane $TA[4]$

By calculation, G has $10n$ vertices and $13n - 1$ edges. Also by calculation, we obtain three edge partitions of G

based on the degrees of the end vertices of each edge as follows:

$$E_1 = \{uv \in E(G) \mid d_G(u)=2, d_G(v)=3\}, |E_1| = 6n + 6.$$

$$E_2 = \{uv \in E(G) \mid d_G(u)=2, d_G(v)=4\}, |E_2| = 6n - 6.$$

$$E_3 = \{uv \in E(G) \mid d_G(u)=d_G(v) = 4\}, |E_3| = n - 1.$$

Therefore, in $TA[n]$, there are three types of edges based on the temperature of end vertices of each edge as follows:

$$TE_1 = \{uv \in E(G) \mid T(u) = \frac{2}{10n-2}, T(v) = \frac{3}{10n-3}\}, |E_1| = 6n$$

+ 6.

$$TE_2 = \{uv \in E(G) \mid T(u) = \frac{2}{10n-2}, T(v) = \frac{4}{10n-4}\}, |E_2| = 6n$$

- 6.

$$TE_3 = \{uv \in E(G) \mid T(u) = T(v) = \frac{4}{10n-4}\}, |E_3| = n - 1.$$

Theorem 1. The temperature Sombor index of a tetrameric 1,3-adamantane $TA [n]$ is

$$\begin{aligned} TSO(TA[n]) &= \left[\frac{1}{(5n-1)^2} + \frac{9}{(10n-3)^2} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} (6n+6) \\ &+ \left[\frac{1}{(5n-1)^2} + \frac{4}{(5n-2)^2} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} (6n-6) \\ &+ \left[\frac{8}{(5n-2)^2} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} (n-1). \end{aligned}$$

Proof: To compute $TSO(TA [n])$, we see that

$$\begin{aligned} TSO(TA[n]) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [T(u)^2 + T(v)^2]^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ &= \left[\left(\frac{1}{5n-1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{3}{10n-3} \right)^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} (6n+6) \\ &+ \left[\left(\frac{2}{10n-2} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{4}{10n-4} \right)^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} (6n-6) \\ &+ \left[\left(\frac{4}{10n-4} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{4}{10n-4} \right)^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} (n-1) \\ &= \left[\frac{1}{(5n-1)^2} + \frac{9}{(10n-3)^2} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} (6n+6) \\ &+ \left[\frac{1}{(5n-1)^2} + \frac{4}{(5n-2)^2} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} (6n-6) \end{aligned}$$

$$+ \left[\frac{8}{(5n-2)^2} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} (n-1).$$

Theorem 2. The modified temperature Sombor index of a tetrameric 1,3-adamantane $TA [n]$ is

$$\begin{aligned} {}^m TSO(TA[n]) &= \left[\frac{1}{(5n-1)^2} + \frac{9}{(10n-3)^2} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} (6n+6) \\ &+ \left[\frac{1}{(5n-1)^2} + \frac{4}{(5n-2)^2} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} (6n-6) \\ &+ \left[\frac{8}{(5n-2)^2} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} (n-1). \end{aligned}$$

Proof: To compute ${}^m TSO(TA[n])$, we see that

$$\begin{aligned} {}^m TSO(TA[n]) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [T(u)^2 + T(v)^2]^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ &= \left[\left(\frac{1}{5n-1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{3}{10n-3} \right)^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} (6n+6) \\ &+ \left[\left(\frac{2}{10n-2} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{4}{10n-4} \right)^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} (6n-6) \\ &+ \left[\left(\frac{4}{10n-4} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{4}{10n-4} \right)^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} (n-1) \\ &= \left[\frac{1}{(5n-1)^2} + \frac{9}{(10n-3)^2} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} (6n+6) \\ &+ \left[\frac{1}{(5n-1)^2} + \frac{4}{(5n-2)^2} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} (6n-6) \\ &+ \left[\frac{8}{(5n-2)^2} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} (n-1). \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3. The temperature Nirmala index of a tetrameric 1,3-adamantane $TA [n]$ is

$$\begin{aligned} TN(TA[n]) &= \left[\frac{25n-6}{(5n-1)(10n-3)} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} (6n+6) \\ &+ \left[\frac{15n-4}{(5n-1)(5n-2)} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} (6n-6) + \left(\frac{4}{5n-2} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} (n-1). \end{aligned}$$

Proof: To compute $TN(TA[n])$, we see that

$$\begin{aligned} TN(TA[n]) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [T(u) + T(v)]^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ &= \left[\left(\frac{1}{5n-1} \right) + \left(\frac{3}{10n-3} \right) \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} (6n+6) \\ &+ \left[\left(\frac{2}{10n-2} \right) + \left(\frac{4}{10n-4} \right) \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} (6n-6) \\ &+ \left[\left(\frac{4}{10n-4} \right) + \left(\frac{4}{10n-4} \right) \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} (n-1) \\ &= \left[\frac{25n-6}{(5n-1)(10n-3)} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} (6n+6) \\ &+ \left[\frac{15n-4}{(5n-1)(5n-2)} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} (6n-6) + \left(\frac{4}{5n-2} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} (n-1). \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, we can find the values of $TSO(TA[n], x)$, ${}^m TSO(TA[n], x)$ and $TN(TA[n], x)$.

IV. MATHEMATICAL PROPERTIES

Theorem 4. Let G be a connected graph with m edges. Then

$$TSO(G) \leq \sqrt{2mFT(G)}.$$

Proof: Using the Cauchy-Schwarz inequality, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\sum_{uv \in E(G)} \sqrt{T(u)^2 + T(v)^2} \right)^2 &\leq \sum_{uv \in E(G)} 1 \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [T(u)^2 + T(v)^2] \\ &= 2mFT(G). \end{aligned}$$

Thus $TSO(G) \leq \sqrt{2mFT(G)}$.

Theorem 5. Let G be a connected graph. Then

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} T_1(G) \leq TSO(G) \leq T_1(G).$$

Proof: For any two positive numbers a and b ,

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(a+b) \leq \sqrt{a^2 + b^2} \leq a+b.$$

For $a=T(u)$ and $b=T(v)$, the above inequality becomes

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(T(u)+T(v)) \leq \sqrt{(T(u)^2 + T(v)^2)} \leq (T(u)+T(v)).$$

By the definitions, we have

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [T(u)+T(v)] \leq \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \sqrt{T(u)^2 + T(v)^2}$$

$$\leq \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [T(u)+T(v)].$$

Thus we get the desired result.

Theorem 6. Let G be connected graph of order n and size m . Then

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} TMPI(G) \leq TN(G) \leq TMPI(G).$$

Proof: Let a and b be any two non-negative real numbers. Then

$$\sqrt{a+b} \geq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(\sqrt{a} + \sqrt{b})$$

with equality if and only if $a = b$.

If $a = T(u)$ and $b = T(v)$, then the above inequality becomes

$$\sqrt{T(u)+T(v)} \geq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(\sqrt{T(u)} + \sqrt{T(v)}).$$

By the definition of Nirmala index, we have

$$\begin{aligned} TN(G) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \sqrt{T(u)+T(v)} \\ &\geq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(\sqrt{T(u)} + \sqrt{T(v)}) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} TMPI(G). \end{aligned}$$

Also, by the definition of Nirmala index, we have

$$\begin{aligned} TN(G) &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \sqrt{T(u)+T(v)} \\ &= \sum_{uv \in E(G)} \left[(\sqrt{T(u)} + \sqrt{T(v)})^2 - 2\sqrt{T(u)T(v)} \right]^{1/2} \\ &\leq \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (\sqrt{T(u)} + \sqrt{T(v)}) = TMPI(G). \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 7. Let G be a connected graph. Then

$$\begin{aligned} T_1(G) - 2ISI_T(G) &< TSO(G) \\ &\leq \sqrt{2}T_1(G) - 2\sqrt{2}ISI_T(G). \end{aligned}$$

Proof: For any two numbers $a, b > 0$, we have

$$a^2 + b^2 < (a+b)^2 \leq 2(a^2 + b^2).$$

Thus $\sqrt{a^2 + b^2} < a+b \leq \sqrt{2}\sqrt{a^2 + b^2}$ and

$$\begin{aligned} (T(u)+T(v))^2 &= \sqrt{T(u)^2 + T(v)^2} \sqrt{T(u)^2 + T(v)^2} \\ &+ 2T(u)T(v). \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Thus } (T(u)+T(v))^2 &< (T(u)+T(v))\sqrt{T(u)^2 + T(v)^2} \end{aligned}$$

$$+2T(u)T(v).$$

Hence $(T(u)+T(v))$

$$< \sqrt{T(u)^2 + T(v)^2} + \frac{2T(u)T(v)}{T(u)+T(v)}.$$

By the definitions, we have

$$T_1(G) < TSO(G) + 2ISI_T(G).$$

Also we have

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(T(u)+T(v))\sqrt{T(u)^2 + T(v)^2} + 2T(u)T(v) \leq (T(u)+T(v))^2.$$

Thus

$$\sqrt{T(u)^2 + T(v)^2} + \frac{2\sqrt{2}T(u)T(v)}{T(u)+T(v)} \leq \sqrt{2}(T(u)+T(v)).$$

By the definitions, we have

$$TSO(G) + 2\sqrt{2}ISI_T(G) \leq \sqrt{2}T_1(G).$$

This completes the proof.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have introduced the temperature Sombor index, the modified temperature Sombor index and temperature Nirmala index of a graph. We have computed these indices for some standard graphs and tetrameric 1,3-adamantane $TA[n]$. Also we have obtained some properties of the temperature Sombor index and the temperature Nirmala index.

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